

Connection-Emotion-Action (CEA): An Emergent Theory on Teaching Internship Programs

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Abstract:

In today's rapidly evolving educational landscape, effective teaching is essential for fostering students' intellectual and personal growth. As educational theories and practices continue to evolve, so does the demand for competent and skilled teachers who can adapt to these changes and meet the diverse needs of students. However, there is a notable research gap concerning the overall experiences of teaching interns in the internship program of teacher education institutions. Hence, a contextualistic theory was developed through axiomatic approach on three significant components of teaching internship. Based on the sets of axioms developed, the emerged theory states that the integration of pedagogical partnership, emotional dimension recognition, and action research within the teaching internship program fosters the holistic development and professional growth of pre-service teachers, enabling them to: (a) navigate the complexities of the teaching profession, (b) develop reflective teaching practices, and (c) enhance their pedagogical skills to effectively engage with students and stakeholders in the ever-evolving educational landscape. Future directions for theory verification are proposed to validate the emerged theory. Finally, when the theory is validated, it will serve as a foundation in the derivation of other theories in other fields.

Keywords: action research, deductive axiomatic approach, emotional dimension, pedagogical partnership

Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving educational landscape, effective teaching is essential for fostering students' intellectual and personal growth. As educational theories and practices continue to evolve, so does the demand for competent and skilled teachers who can adapt to these changes and meet the diverse needs of students. Teacher education institutions play a critical role in preparing aspiring educators for the challenges of the profession, and one significant component of their training is the teaching internship program.

The teaching internship program plays a crucial role in shaping the development of prospective teachers, providing them with valuable hands-on experience in a classroom setting (Pogoy & Su, 2014). Previous researches have highlighted the positive impact of teaching internships on pre-service teachers, equipping them with essential skills to navigate the challenges of the teaching profession (O'Neill, 2018; Kabilan, 2013; Darling-Hammond, 2006). However, there is a notable research gap concerning the overall experiences of teaching interns in the internship program of teacher education institutions.

The COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted traditional education methods worldwide, leading to a significant increase in online learning as schools and universities closed their doors (Dhawan, 2020; UNESCO, 2020). This shift has had profound implications for teaching interns, necessitating a comprehensive understanding of their experiences during this transitional period. Notably, pre-service teachers who completed their practicum course online encountered various challenges, adaptational gaps, and potential areas for improvement (Özmantar, 2021; Mohebi et al., 2022; Kiok et al., 2021).

In the context of the Philippines, the pandemic has significantly impacted education, affecting over 27 million learners through school closures (UNICEF, 2021). Pre-service teachers in the Philippines faced numerous difficulties during their online teaching practicum, including time management, technological issues, and student concerns. While some coping strategies were employed during the pandemic, there is a clear need to develop post-pandemic measures to support teaching interns effectively (Reyes, 2023).

Responding to this need, the Department of Education (DepEd) and the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) have released policies and guidelines to guide teacher education institutions (TEIs) in deploying pre-service teachers for field study and teaching internships in the post-pandemic era (JCDMO 1, s. 2021). Localized policies and guidelines were also formulated for pre-service teachers' field study and teaching internship as part of the experiential learning courses (DepEd, 2022). The policies and guidelines listed the roles and responsibilities expected of sending TEIs,

teaching interns, and the DepEd and documentary requirements before, during, and after deployment. TEIs and cooperating schools are enjoined to implement in the delivery of teaching internship and field study courses to promote the well-being of students and guarantee quality of exposure.

Despite the existence of policies and guidelines, it is imperative to conduct a study on teaching internship experiences, considering the entire program, including both online and offline components, to create a testable theory for the next-normal. By shedding light on this area, this research will highlight the importance of understanding the challenges and opportunities faced by teaching interns throughout the internship program. The results of this study will inform teacher education programs and institutions on how to develop teaching internship programs that are crisis-ready and better support the needs of pre-service teachers in similar situations in the future.

To achieve the objectives of this study, a deductive axiomatic approach will be employed. This framework will enable the systematic analysis and interpretation of the collected data, drawing upon established principles and axioms in the field of teaching internships in teacher education programs. By utilizing this framework, the study aims to generate a theory that contribute to the existing body of knowledge of the field of education and informs teacher education programs and institutions on developing effective teaching internship programs.

Review of Previous Studies and Accepted Principles

The teaching internship program plays a vital role in the development of prospective teachers, offering them practical experience and the opportunity to apply their theoretical knowledge in real classroom settings. This systematic writing aims to synthesize findings from multiple studies to explore the different perspectives and outcomes associated with teaching internships.

Filipino prospective teachers perceive teaching internships as a multifaceted experience (Rogayan & Reusia, 2021). They view it as an opportunity for continuous learning, a rewarding challenge, a chance to fulfill a surrogate parental role, and a pathway to enhancing pedagogical competence. These perspectives should serve as a basis for further research and prompt teacher education institutions to align their teaching internship programs with the evolving demands of the 21st-century learning landscape and the VUCAD2 (volatile, uncertain, complex, ambiguous, disruptive, and diverse) world. The metaphoric representations of teaching internship held by students can significantly influence their engagement in the teaching career after graduation.

The importance of cooperating teachers in facilitating student-teaching success is also a success factor (Ganal & Andaya, 2015). The personal and professional qualities of student teachers, combined with the guidance and training provided by cooperating teachers, significantly influence the development of teaching skills and the overall experience of student teachers. Positive experiences during student teaching can foster a genuine love for teaching and contribute to the effectiveness of student teachers in managing classroom discipline and related functions. The competencies of cooperating teachers are crucial in cultivating these qualities in student teachers, which can be reflected in their performance and grades.

Practice teaching, as highlighted by, provides interns with practical classroom teaching experience and prepares them for the challenges of managing school activities. Interns are exposed to real-life teaching scenarios, forcing them to embody the role of a teacher in uncontrolled situations. Through practice teaching, interns gain valuable management skills, assuming responsibilities similar to those of actual teachers. The diverse school environments, protocols, and learning resources encountered during practice teaching contribute to a varied range of personal experiences. However, common phenomena observed among interns can serve as strong determinants for addressing issues and implementing appropriate actions (Gula & Nunez, 2022).

The teaching internship program offers numerous benefits to teaching interns. Mangila (2018) emphasized that the program provides an opportunity to put theoretical skills into practice, allowing interns to experience the realities of teaching firsthand. Anar et al. (2017) further highlighted that teaching internships enable students to enhance their abilities, apply classroom learning, and gain experience in lesson preparation, authentic teaching, and student assessment. This industry-based experience, as indicated by CMO no. 104 series of 2017, complements formal learning by equipping teaching interns with practical knowledge, competencies, attitudes, and desirable professional interests. Magday and Pramoolsook (2020) emphasized that the teaching internship program offers a satisfying and relevant internship experience, facilitating the acquisition of professional ideals, character, and skills.

Kolb's (1984) experiential learning theory provides a valuable framework for understanding the role of teaching internships in the development of prospective teachers. According to Kolb, learning is a cyclical process that involves four stages: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. These stages highlight the importance of engaging in real-world experiences, reflecting on those experiences, abstractly conceptualizing the knowledge gained, and then applying that knowledge in new situations. Kolb's experiential learning theory underscores the significance of teaching internships as a platform for prospective teachers to engage in concrete experiences, reflect on those experiences, connect theory and practice, and actively

experiment with different teaching approaches. By incorporating the principles of experiential learning into teaching internship programs, teacher education institutions can facilitate the holistic development of future educators and prepare them to thrive in diverse and dynamic classrooms.

The teaching internship program serves as a significant component of teacher education, providing prospective teachers with practical experience and a platform to apply theoretical knowledge. When viewed through the lens of Kolb's experiential learning theory, the metaphoric lens through which Filipino prospective teachers perceive teaching internships, the role of cooperating teachers, the importance of practice teaching, and the various benefits of the program can be better understood in the context of the learning process.

Incorporating these insights from Kolb's experiential learning theory into the design and implementation of teaching internship programs can lead to more effective teacher education. By recognizing these areas, teacher education institutions can create internship programs that better support the pedagogical skills and professional development of prospective teachers. This integration can contribute to the production of globally competitive and industry-ready educators in the future.

It is, therefore, assumed that ***teaching internship programs offer prospective teachers practical experiences (Axiom 1).***

The teaching internship program plays a crucial role in shaping the experiences and professional development of pre-service teachers.

Baylan (2019) highlighted the significance of pedagogical partnership, emphasizing the role of a healthy communication climate in fostering effective teaching and learning experiences. This partnership between interns and mentors influences instructional approaches and the design of instructional aids. It nurtures reflective teaching practices and encourages the development of a network of active peer-to-peer learning, ultimately shaping the teaching interns' pedagogical skills and professional growth. Furthermore, Rahmawati et al. (2021) underscored the emotional dimension of the teaching practicum, asserting that pre-service teachers undergo a range of emotions as they engage with mentor teachers, students, and their peers. These emotional experiences, both positive and negative, contribute to their motivations, attitudes, and professional learning. Understanding and examining the emotional aspects of the practicum are crucial for supporting pre-service teachers' holistic development, recognizing that teaching is not solely about technical skills but also involves social and emotional processes.

Moreover, authentic teaching practice plays a pivotal role in shaping teacher efficacy. Bandura emphasizes that pre-service teachers benefit from experiencing success in authentic settings, which builds strong feelings of teacher efficacy. Authentic teaching experiences allow pre-service teachers to face challenges, develop coping strategies, and overcome adversity, ultimately establishing stronger beliefs in their teaching efficacy (Redmon, 2007; Gurvitch & Metzler, 2009).

Daniel Goleman's theory of emotional intelligence provides valuable insights into understanding the emotional dimension of pre-service teachers during the teaching practicum. Goleman defined emotional intelligence as the ability to recognize, understand, and manage emotions effectively, both in oneself and in others (Resilient Educator, 2020). In the context of teaching, emotional intelligence is essential for fostering positive teacher-student relationships, creating a supportive classroom climate, and effectively managing classroom dynamics. The emotional experiences that pre-service teachers encounter during their teaching internships have a significant impact on their motivation, attitudes, and overall development as educators.

During the teaching practicum, pre-service teachers interact with various stakeholders, including mentor teachers, students, and their peers. These interactions elicit a range of emotions, such as excitement, frustration, anxiety, and satisfaction. The ability to recognize and understand these emotions is crucial for pre-service teachers to navigate the challenges of the classroom effectively. Emotional intelligence enables them to respond appropriately to students' emotional needs, regulate their own emotions during challenging situations, and maintain a positive and supportive learning environment.

The teaching internship program, with its focus on pedagogical partnership, emotional experiences, and authentic teaching practice, aligns with the principles of Daniel Goleman's theory of emotional intelligence. Understanding the interconnected aspects of pedagogical partnership, emotional experiences, and authentic teaching practice allows for the creation of a supportive learning environment. This environment promotes the development of emotional intelligence, empowering pre-service teachers to effectively recognize and manage their emotions, establish positive teacher-student relationships, and navigate the complex emotional landscape of the classroom. Ultimately, by embracing these perspectives, teacher education programs foster the holistic growth and professional success of future educators.

It appears then that ***the emotional dimension of pre-service teachers plays a crucial role during the teaching internship program (Axiom 2).***

Axiom 1 emphasizes the importance of pedagogical partnership and authentic teaching experiences in the teaching internship program for pre-service teachers. However, it is necessary to appeal to Axiom 2 to further enhance the effectiveness of the program. As highlighted in Rahmawati et al. (2021), the emotional dimension plays a significant role in pre-service teachers' motivations, attitudes, and professional learning. By recognizing and addressing the emotional experiences that pre-service teachers encounter during the teaching practicum, teacher education programs can provide the necessary support and guidance to foster their holistic development as educators.

When pre-service teachers' emotional experiences are acknowledged, they are better equipped to navigate the challenges they face in the classroom. By addressing emotional constraints and providing strategies to manage them, teacher education programs can help pre-service teachers develop resilience and emotional well-being, ultimately enhancing their ability to engage effectively with students, mentor teachers, and other stakeholders. This aligns with the overarching goal of the teaching internship program, as highlighted in Axiom 1, to enhance pedagogical skills and professional development.

In addition to addressing the emotional dimension, integrating action research into the teaching internship program further supports the professional development of pre-service teachers (JCDMO No. 1, series of 2021). It is imperative to highlight that all of the teacher education curricula from 1999 to 2017 requires the completion of action research during the internship (CMO Nos. 74-80, and 82, series of 2017).

Action research serves as a powerful tool for professional development in the teaching internship program. Pre-service teachers engage in systematic examination and improvement of their teaching practice through action research. This integration empowers pre-service teachers to become active participants in their own professional growth, contributing to a career-long process of development and refinement (Smith & Sela, 2005). Action research bridges the gap between research and practice, providing opportunities for critical reflection and improvement (Hine, 2013).

Moreover, studies highlight the authentic nature of action research as a capstone assessment in the teaching internship program (Maxwell, 2012). Action research reports demonstrate student engagement with the challenges of the profession and tangible evidence of improvement in understandings, knowledge, and skills. Participatory action research has also been found effective in teacher development, fostering collaboration, confidence, and sustained motivation (Tirol et al., 2022). By incorporating action research, the teaching internship program enables pre-service teachers to appreciate and observe the real classroom setting while critically reflecting on their practice (Hine, 2013).

Gibb's (1998, as cited in Markkanen et al., 2022) reflective cycle theory provides a valuable framework for understanding and analyzing the process of reflective practice in action research during a teaching internship. The first stage of the cycle is the description of the experience, where teaching interns can document and outline the details of their action research project. This may include the objectives, methodologies, and data collection strategies employed during the research. By systematically describing their experience, teaching interns gain a clearer understanding of the context and factors influencing their research. Teaching interns can engage in a systematic process of reflection, which aligns with the principles of action research. Through this reflective practice, teaching interns can identify areas for improvement, modify their instructional strategies, and make informed decisions to enhance their teaching practices.

This integration of action research and reflective practice in the teaching internship program contributes to the development of reflective practitioners who continuously seek to improve their teaching skills and enhance student learning outcomes.

With these, it can be assumed that ***the integration of action research in the teaching internship program facilitates growth of teaching interns as reflective practitioners (Axiom 3).***

Axiom 1 emphasizes the significance of pedagogical partnership and authentic teaching experiences in enhancing pre-service teachers' pedagogical skills and professional development. Axiom 2 highlights the importance of recognizing and addressing the emotional dimension of pre-service teachers during the teaching practicum, fostering their motivation and holistic development as educators. To further strengthen the teaching internship program, it is necessary to assume Axiom 3, which advocates for the integration of action research.

Axiom 3 assumes that the integration of action research in the teaching internship program facilitates the growth of pre-service teachers as reflective practitioners (Smith & Sela, 2005). Action research encourages pre-service teachers to engage in a cyclical process of inquiry, reflection, and improvement (Maxwell, 2012). By actively engaging in action research, pre-service teachers develop a deeper understanding of their own teaching practices, make informed decisions, and adapt their strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students (Hine, 2013).

Assuming Axiom 3 in relation to Axioms 1 and 2 is necessary to strengthen the teaching internship program. The integration of action research provides pre-service teachers with a structured framework to reflect on their teaching experiences, address emotional constraints, and continuously improve their pedagogical skills (Smith & Sela, 2005). By engaging in action research, pre-service teachers become reflective practitioners committed to their own professional growth and the improvement of their instructional practices (Maxwell, 2012).

Assuming Axiom 3, which advocates for the integration of action research, enhances the teaching internship program by providing pre-service teachers with a structured framework for reflective practice and continuous improvement. By engaging in action research, pre-service teachers develop a deeper understanding of their teaching practices and make evidence-based decisions to enhance their pedagogical skills (Hine, 2013; Maxwell, 2012). This integration supports the goals of Axioms 1 and 2 by fostering pedagogical development and addressing the emotional dimension of pre-service teachers, ultimately strengthening the overall effectiveness and impact of the teaching internship program.

These axioms collectively highlight the importance of fostering pedagogical partnership, addressing emotional constraints, and promoting authentic teaching experiences to enhance the effectiveness of the teaching internship program and promote the professional development of pre-service teachers.

Development of Propositions

The formulation of the propositions leads to theory generation for the teaching internship program. The developed propositions and theory encompass the integration of research, the recognition of the emotional dimension, and the promotion of pedagogical partnership and authentic teaching experiences, to enhance the holistic development and professional growth of pre-service teachers.

The formulation of the three axioms led the researcher to construct two propositions. These propositions are as follows:

1. The integration of action research in the teaching internship program, supported by a pedagogical partnership between mentors and interns, enhances reflective practice among teaching interns (Axiom 1 and Axiom 3).
2. Addressing the emotional dimension of pre-service teachers within a supportive pedagogical partnership enhances their motivation, well-being, and holistic development as reflective practitioners (Axiom 2 and Axiom 3).

These propositions highlight the interplay between action research, pedagogical partnership, and emotional experiences within the teaching internship program. By integrating action research and fostering a supportive pedagogical partnership, teaching interns are empowered to reflect on their teaching practices, make improvements, and navigate the emotional challenges they encounter during their teaching practicum. This integration promotes the holistic development, professional growth, and well-being of pre-service teachers, ultimately preparing them to become effective and resilient educators.

Based on axioms 1 and 3, **proposition 1** was formulated which states that:

The integration of action research in the teaching internship program, supported by a pedagogical partnership between mentors and interns, enhances reflective practice among teaching interns.

The integration of action research within the teaching internship program serves as a powerful tool for promoting reflective practice and continuous improvement among teaching interns. Action research, as highlighted in Axiom 1 (Smith & Sela, 2005; Maxwell, 2012; Hine, 2013), enables teaching interns to actively engage in a cyclical process of inquiry, reflection, and improvement. By systematically examining their teaching practices, teaching interns can gain a deeper understanding of their instructional approaches and make informed decisions to enhance their pedagogical skills (Maxwell, 2012).

The pedagogical partnership between mentors and interns plays a crucial role in supporting the integration of action research and fostering reflective practice. This partnership, as emphasized in Axiom 3 (Baylan, 2019; Ganal & Andaya, 2015; Gula & Nunez, 2022), provides a supportive framework for teaching interns to collaborate with experienced mentors, exchange ideas, and receive guidance throughout their teaching internship journey. Mentors can serve as valuable resources, offering insights and feedback to help teaching interns refine their action research projects and make meaningful improvements in their teaching practices (Baylan, 2019).

Through the integration of action research and the pedagogical partnership, teaching interns engage in authentic teaching experiences that allow for the application of theoretical knowledge in real classroom settings. This experiential learning approach, as indicated in Axiom 1 (Smith & Sela, 2005; Maxwell, 2012; Hine, 2013), provides teaching interns with opportunities to bridge the gap between theory and practice, deepening their understanding of effective teaching strategies and instructional design. By actively implementing their action research projects in the

classroom, teaching interns can evaluate the impact of their instructional approaches, reflect on the outcomes, and make informed adjustments to improve their teaching practices (Hine, 2013).

The combination of action research and the pedagogical partnership supports teaching interns in their journey towards becoming reflective practitioners. As teaching interns engage in reflective practice, they can critically evaluate their teaching methods, identify areas for growth, and develop innovative solutions to address challenges in the classroom (Maxwell, 2012). This reflective process, guided by the pedagogical partnership, fosters a culture of continuous improvement among teaching interns, encouraging them to strive for excellence and lifelong professional development (Ganal & Andaya, 2015).

Proposition 1 highlights the significance of integrating action research and the pedagogical partnership within the teaching internship program. This integration provides teaching interns with a structured framework for reflective practice and continuous improvement, enabling them to bridge the gap between theory and practice, enhance their pedagogical skills, and make meaningful improvements in their teaching practices. By engaging in authentic teaching experiences and receiving guidance from experienced mentors, teaching interns are empowered to become reflective practitioners committed to ongoing professional growth (Axiom 1 and Axiom 3). Furthermore, based on axioms 2 and 3, **proposition 2** was postulated which states that:

Addressing the emotional dimension of teaching interns, within the framework of a supportive pedagogical partnership, promotes their motivation, well-being, and holistic development as reflective practitioners.

The emotional dimension of pre-service teachers during the teaching practicum plays a significant role in their motivation, well-being, and overall development as educators. As emphasized in Axiom 2 (Rahmawati et al., 2021), pre-service teachers experience a range of emotions as they engage with mentor teachers, students, and their peers during their teaching practicum. Understanding and acknowledging these emotional experiences are crucial for supporting the holistic development and well-being of pre-service teachers, as they navigate the challenges and complexities of the teaching profession.

The pedagogical partnership between mentors and pre-service teachers, as highlighted in Axiom 3 (Baylan, 2019; Ganal & Andaya, 2015; Gula & Nunez, 2022), provides a supportive framework for addressing the emotional dimension of pre-service teachers during the teaching practicum. Within this partnership, mentors can play a crucial role in creating a safe and nurturing environment where pre-service teachers feel comfortable expressing and reflecting on their emotions (Baylan, 2019). By establishing open lines of communication and offering guidance, mentors can help pre-service teachers navigate the emotional challenges they encounter, validate their experiences, and provide support and encouragement (Ganal & Andaya, 2015).

Addressing the emotional dimension of pre-service teachers contributes to their motivation and overall well-being. When pre-service teachers' emotional experiences are acknowledged and supported, they are better equipped to navigate the challenges they face in the classroom and maintain their enthusiasm for teaching (Rahmawati et al., 2021). The recognition and validation of emotions can enhance pre-service teachers' sense of belonging and engagement, ultimately fostering their motivation to persist and succeed in the teaching profession.

Furthermore, attending to the emotional dimension within the pedagogical partnership promotes the holistic development of pre-service teachers as reflective practitioners. By reflecting on their emotional experiences, pre-service teachers can gain deeper insights into their own emotions and their impact on their teaching practices (Baylan, 2019). This reflective process, guided by the pedagogical partnership, allows pre-service teachers to develop emotional intelligence, self-awareness, and resilience, which are essential qualities for effective teaching (Ganal & Andaya, 2015).

Proposition 2 emphasizes the importance of recognizing and addressing the emotional dimension of pre-service teachers during the teaching practicum, within the framework of a supportive pedagogical partnership. By creating a safe and nurturing environment that acknowledges and supports pre-service teachers' emotions, mentors can promote their motivation, well-being, and holistic development as reflective practitioners (Axiom 2 and Axiom 3). Through this approach, pre-service teachers can navigate the emotional challenges of the teaching profession, develop emotional intelligence, and cultivate the resilience needed to thrive as educators.

Connection-Emotion-Action (CEA) Theory of Teaching Internship Programs

The Connection-Emotion-Action (CEA) Theory of internship programs is a contextualistic theory that highlights the integration of collaborative partnership (**connection**), emotional dimension recognition (**emotion**), and research application (**action**) within the internship program, as follows:

The integration of pedagogical partnership, emotional dimension recognition, and action research within teaching internship program fosters the holistic development and professional growth of interns,

enabling them to: (a) navigate the complexities of their respective fields, (b) develop reflective practices, and (c) enhance their skills to effectively engage with individuals and stakeholders in the ever-evolving educational landscape.

The **CEA Theory is contextualistic**. This means that the three elements of the theory (collaborative partnerships, emotional intelligence, and practical application) are not considered separate entities, but are interconnected and interdependent. The meaning and significance of each element are influenced by the specific context in which the internship takes place.

For example, the meaning of pedagogical partnership is different for a teaching intern deployed at a relatively big school than it is for a teaching intern deployed at a small school. The emotional dimension of teaching is also different for a teaching intern who is teaching a class of students with special needs than it is for a teaching intern who is teaching a class of typical students. And the meaning of action research is different for a teaching intern who is working in a school with a strong culture of collaboration than it is for a teaching intern who is working in a school with a more individualistic culture.

Another instance, the nature of collaborative partnerships may differ for an intern placed in a large corporation compared to one placed in a small start-up. Similarly, the emotional intelligence required may vary for an intern working with diverse populations versus one working in a homogeneous environment. Additionally, the meaning of practical application may change for an intern in an organization with a strong team-oriented culture versus one in a more individualistic setting.

The CEA theory acknowledges the importance of context in understanding the meaning of the three elements, making it a more complex yet realistic theory. It recognizes that professional environments are multifaceted and constantly evolving, and that interns must be equipped with the skills to navigate different contexts successfully.

Figure 1. Connection-Emotion-Action (CEA) Theory of Teaching Internship Programs

The **CEA Theory has three components** that are seen as essential for the holistic development and professional growth of teaching interns. These components enable interns to develop the competencies necessary for success in their respective fields. By fostering collaborative relationships, understanding emotional intelligence, and engaging in action research or research in general, interns can develop the comprehensive skills they need to excel in their chosen professions.

The first component, collaborative partnerships (*connection*), refers to the relationship between interns and their mentors or supervisors. This relationship provides interns with the opportunity to learn from experienced professionals and receive feedback on their work. The second component, emotional intelligence (*emotion*), involves recognizing and understanding the emotional experiences interns encounter during their internship. Institutions or programs can provide the necessary support and guidance to foster interns' emotional growth and development. The third component, research application (*action*), encourages interns to engage in hands-on learning and continuous improvement. Through this process, interns gain a deeper understanding of their field, make informed decisions, and adapt their strategies to meet the diverse needs of their professional environment.

By incorporating the principles of the CEA Theory into the design and implementation of internship programs, educational institutions can enhance the effectiveness and impact of their programs. This, in turn, produces competent and reflective professionals who are equipped to meet the evolving needs of the professional landscape.

The diagram presented in Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual framework of the Connection-Emotion-Action (CEA) Theory in the context of a teaching internship program. This diagram visually represents the interplay among collaborative partnerships (*connection*), emotional intelligence (*emotion*), and research application (*action*) within the internship experience. The components of the CEA Theory are depicted as interconnected elements, highlighting their integration and mutual influence in fostering the holistic development and professional growth of interns.

The diagram serves as a visual representation of the CEA Theory, demonstrating the interconnectedness and interdependence of the key components that contribute to the transformative nature of teaching internship programs. It emphasizes the importance of harnessing the power of collaboration, emotional intelligence, and practical application in preparing interns for the complexities of their chosen fields.

By extension, **CEA Theory is applicable to all types of student internship programs in the Philippines** including immersion programs, on-the-job training, and other similar experiences. Regardless of the specific format or field of study, the integration of collaborative partnerships, emotional intelligence, and research application remains relevant and beneficial for the holistic development of interns.

In immersion programs, where students are fully immersed in a particular environment or culture, the CEA Theory can guide students in establishing meaningful connections with mentors or supervisors. These collaborative partnerships can provide students with valuable guidance and support as they navigate the intricacies of the immersion experience. Additionally, recognizing and understanding the emotional dimension of being immersed in a new environment can help students adapt and thrive in unfamiliar circumstances. By engaging in practical research application, students can actively apply their knowledge and skills to real-world scenarios, further enhancing their learning and growth during the immersion program.

Similarly, in on-the-job training programs, the CEA Theory can be applied to foster the development of students' professional competencies. Collaborative partnerships with experienced professionals can provide students with mentorship and guidance as they learn the ropes of their chosen field. Understanding the emotional dimension of working in a professional setting, such as managing stress or handling workplace relationships, can contribute to students' overall effectiveness and well-being during their internship. Finally, engaging in practical research application allows students to actively participate in meaningful projects or tasks. This enables them to gain hands-on experience and refines their skills within the context of their chosen profession.

By applying the principles of the CEA Theory to all types of student internship programs, educational institutions can create comprehensive and transformative experiences for their students. These programs can facilitate the development of students' professional competencies, foster reflective practices, and enhance their ability to effectively engage with stakeholders in their respective fields. Whether it is an immersion program, on-the-job training, or any other type of student internship, the CEA Theory provides a framework for guiding students' holistic growth and preparing them for success in their future careers.

References

- Añar, L. E., Petersen, R. J., & Villanca, A. (2017). The learning experiences of Filipino pre-service teachers in the Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) program of a Thai elementary school. *Asia Pacific Journal of Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 14, 27-44. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/b6cb/b36e1dcfe05c1c08110236e159a0e3557de3.pdf>.
- Baylan, S. L. (2019). A qualitative study of teacher interns' experiences of pair teaching during teaching practice sessions. *International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Field*, 5(6), 197-205.
- CHED Memorandum Order No. 74, series of 2017. *Policies, standards and guidelines for Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd)*. <https://ched.gov.ph/w-p-content/uploads/2017/11/CMO-No.-74-s.-2017.pdf>.

- CHED Memorandum Order No. 75, series of 2017. *Policies, standards and guidelines for Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd)*. <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/CMO-No.-75-s.-2017.pdf>.
- CHED Memorandum Order No. 76, series of 2017. *Policies, standards and guidelines for Bachelor of Early Childhood Education (BECEd)*. <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/CMO-No.-76-s.-2017.pdf>.
- CHED Memorandum Order No. 77, series of 2017. *Policies, standards and guidelines for Bachelor of Special Needs Education (BSNEd)*. <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/CMO-No.-77-s.-2017.pdf>.
- CHED Memorandum Order No. 78, series of 2017. *Policies, standards and guidelines for Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education (BTLEd)*. <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/CMO-No.-78-s.-2017.pdf>.
- CHED Memorandum Order No. 79, series of 2017. *Policies, standards and guidelines for Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education (BTVTEd)*. <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/CMO-No.-79-s.-2017.pdf>.
- CHED Memorandum Order No. 80, series of 2017. *Policies, standards and guidelines for Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd)*. <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/CMO-No.-80-s.-2017.pdf>.
- CHED Memorandum Order No. 82, series of 2017. *Policies, standards and guidelines for Bachelor of Culture and Arts Education (BCAEd)*. <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/CMO-No.-82-s.-2017.pdf>.
- CHED Memorandum Order No. 104, series of 2017. *Revised guidelines for Student Internship Program in the Philippines (SIPP) for all programs*. <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/CMO-NO.-104-S.-2017.pdf>.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2006). Constructing 21st-century teacher education. *Journal of Teacher Education, 57*(3), 300-314. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487105285962>.
- Department of Education – Division of Lapu-Lapu City. (2022). *Division policies and guidelines on the deployment of pre-service teachers for Field Study and Teaching Internship*.
- Dhawan, S. (2020). Online learning: A panacea in the time of COVID-19 crisis. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems, 49*(1), 5-22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047239520934018>.
- Ganal, N. & Andaya, O. J. (2015). Problems of prospective teachers of Philippine Normal University, North Luzon Campus during practice teaching. *Asia Pacific Journal of Research*. <https://www.academia.edu/download/48869553/3006201510.pdf>.
- Gurvitch, R., & Metzler, M. W. (2009). The effects of laboratory-based and field-based practicum experience on pre-service teachers' self-efficacy. *Teaching and Teacher Education, 25*(3), 437-443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2008.08.006>.
- Gula, L. & Nuñez, J. (2022). A Collaborative auto-ethnographical study on the emerging phenomena of the 21st century practice-teaching journey. *Partners Universal International Research Journal, 1*(2), 80-91. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6727056>.
- Hine, G. S. (2013). The importance of action research in teacher education programs. *Issues in Educational Research, 23*(2), 151-163.
- Joint CHED-DepEd Memorandum Order No. 1, series of 2021. *Policies and guidelines on the deployment of pre-service teachers for Field Study and Teaching Internship*.
- Kabilan, M. K. (2013). A phenomenological study of an international teaching practicum: Pre-service teachers' experiences of professional development. *Teaching and Teacher Education, 36*, 198-209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2013.07.013>.
- Kiok, P. K., Din, W. A., Said, N., Swanto, S. (2021). The experiences of pre-service teachers teaching practicum during the COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Education, Psychology and Counseling, 6* (43), 280-295. <https://doi.org/10.35631/IJEP.643022>.
- Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential Learning: Experience as the Source of Learning and Development*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
- Magday Jr, W. D. & Pramoolsook, I. (2020). Consistency verification between qualitative entries and quantitative ratings in the teaching evaluation forms of Filipino pre-service teachers. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research, 19*(2), 136-162. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.2.9>.
- Mangila, B. B. (2018). Assessment of pre-service teachers on the practice teaching program: Inputs for program enhancement. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences, 5*(3), 50-58.
- Markkanen, P., Välimäki, M., Anttila, M., & Kuuskorpi, M. (2020). A reflective cycle: Understanding challenging situations in a school setting. *Educational Research, 1-17*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2020.1711790>.

- Maxwell, T. W. (2012). Assessment in higher education in the professions: Action research as an authentic assessment task. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 17(6), 686-696. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2012.725220>.
- Mohebi, L., Elsayary, A., & Meda, L. (2022). *Teacher candidates' perception of their first week school placement: Comparison between online and face-to-face practicum learnings and challenges*. <https://doi.org/10.32744/pse.2022.6.36>.
- O'Neill, S.M. (2018). *Preparing special education teachers to work with low-incidence populations - The teachers' perspectives: A phenomenological study* [Doctoral dissertation, Drexel University]. Drexel University Libraries. <https://doi.org/10.17918/d8q37m>.
- Özmantar, ZK (2021). Practicum experience in the era of new-normal: A phenomenological study. *Educational Planning*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1339170.pdf>.
- Pogoy, A.M. & Su, S.C. (2014). Pre-service teaching of English in Taiwan and the Philippines: A comparative study. *CNU Journal of Higher Education*, 8, 182-194.
- Rahmawati, E., Miftakh, F., & Al-Baekani, A. K. (2021). A Pre-service english teacher's emotional experiences within teaching practicum during COVID-19 pandemic. *INTERACTION: Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa*, 8(2), 277-290. <https://doi.org/10.36232/jurnalpendidikanbahasa.v8i2.1360>.
- Redmon, R. J. (2007). Impact of Teacher Preparation upon Teacher Efficacy. *Online Submission* (ED500013). ERIC. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED500013.pdf>.
- Resilient Educator. (2020, June 11). Daniel Goleman's emotional intelligence theory explained. Retrieved from <https://resilienteducator.com/classroom-resources/daniel-golemans-emotional-intelligence-theory-explained/>
- Reyes, C. (2023). Lived experiences of pre-service English teachers in online teaching internship during COVID 19 pandemic. *Journal for Educators, Teachers and Trainers*, 14(2), 438-447. <https://doi.org/10.47750/jett.2023.14.02.041>.
- Rogayan, D. & Reusia, D. H. (2021). Teaching Internship from the Metaphorical Lens of Filipino Prospective Teachers. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 10(3), 798-806. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v10i3.21242>.
- Smith, K., & Sela, O. (2005). Action research as a bridge between pre-service teacher education and in-service professional development for students and teacher educators. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 28(3), 293-310. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619760500269418>.
- Tirol, S., Cortes, S. T., Tinapay, A., & Samillano, J. (2022). A teacher training program on designing participatory educational action research proposal. *Ho Chi Minh City Open University Journal of Science – Social Sciences*, 12(1), 23-39. <https://doi.org/10.46223/HCMCOUJS.soci.en.12.1.2214.2022>.
- UNESCO. (2020). *Education in a post-COVID world: Nine ideas for public action*. Retrieved from https://en.unesco.org/sites/default/files/education_in_a_post-covid_world-nine_ideas_for_public_action.pdf.
- UNICEF (2021, August 25). *Filipino children continue missing education opportunities in another year of school closure*. <https://www.unicef.org/philippines/press-releases/filipino-children-continue-missing-education-opportunities-another-year-school>.